

Distances on earth's surface

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We compare methods of calculating distances on the earth's surface. We assume that the earth is a revolution ellipsoid [major semiaxis= $a=6378388\text{m}$] or a ball [radius= $R=6371030\text{m}$]. On the ball we can use the cosine law for sides (spherical trigonometry), see Schröer [3] chapter 9. On a revolution ellipsoid there are methods for short, middle and large distances. We present one method and we calculate examples.

We begin with short distances. (L_i, B_i) for $i=1$ and 2 shall be the geographical longitude and latitude, that are known. There is a method from Gauss/Helmert see Schödlbauer [2] chapter C.1.1 p.73,74:

$$\begin{aligned}u &= [1] \cdot \Delta B \cdot (1 + [3] \cdot \Delta L^2 + [4] \cdot \Delta B^2) \\v &= [2] \cdot \Delta L \cdot (1 + [5] \cdot \Delta L^2 + [6] \cdot \Delta B^2) \\ \Delta A &= \sin B \cdot \Delta L \cdot (1 + [7] \cdot \Delta L^2 + [8] \cdot \Delta B^2)\end{aligned}$$

with

$$\Delta B = B_2 - B_1 \quad \Delta L = L_2 - L_1 \quad \rho = \frac{180}{\pi}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned}[1] &= \frac{c}{\rho V^3} & [2] &= \frac{c \cdot \cos B}{\rho V} \\ [3] &= -\frac{\cos^2 B \cdot (2 + 3 \cdot t^2 + 2 \cdot \eta^2)}{24 \cdot \rho^2} & [4] &= \frac{\eta^2 \cdot (1 - t^2)}{8 \cdot \rho^2 \cdot V^4} \\ [5] &= -\frac{\sin^2 B}{24 \cdot \rho^2} & [6] &= \frac{1 + \eta^2 \cdot (1 - 9 \cdot t^2)}{24 \cdot \rho^2 \cdot V^4} \\ [7] &= \frac{\cos^2 B \cdot (1 + \eta^2)}{12 \cdot \rho^2} & [8] &= \frac{3 + 8 \cdot \eta^2}{24 \cdot \rho^2 \cdot V^4}\end{aligned}$$

The quantities mean:

$c = \frac{a^2}{b}$ with the earth's major semiaxis a and the earth's minor semiaxis b
 $e'^2 = \frac{a^2 - b^2}{b^2}$ = square of the second numerical eccentricity

$$\eta^2 = e'^2 \cdot \cos^2 B \quad V^2 = 1 + \eta^2 \quad t = \tan B$$

with $B = \frac{B_1+B_2}{2}$ as average latitude.

We get the searched distance with $S = \sqrt{u^2 + v^2}$. The distances must be smaller than 100km. One example is the distance between Bonn and Düsseldorf. The distance is with the cosine law of sides (spherical trigonometry) 56.900km respectively 56.751km with Gauss/Helmert.

Now we turn to the middle distances between 100km and 1000km with the method from Jordan see Schödlbauer [2] chapter C.2.1 p.84-86:

a) coordinate differences, average latitude

$$\Delta B = B_1 - B_2 \quad \Delta L = L_2 - L_1 \quad B = \frac{B_1 + B_2}{2}$$

b)

$$\bar{B}_1 = \arctan \frac{\tan B_1}{\sqrt{1 + e'^2}}$$

$$\bar{B}_2 = \arctan \frac{\tan B_2}{\sqrt{1 + e'^2}} \quad \bar{B} = \frac{\bar{B}_1 + \bar{B}_2}{2}$$

$$\Delta \bar{L} = v \cdot \Delta L \cdot (1 + \lambda_1 \cdot \Delta B^2 + \lambda_2 \cdot \Delta L^2 + \lambda_3 \cdot \Delta B^4 + \lambda_4 \cdot \Delta B^2 \cdot \Delta L^2 + \lambda_5 \cdot \Delta L^4)$$

$$\lambda_1 = -\frac{n^2}{24 \cdot \rho^2 \cdot v^4} \cdot \{1 + 3 \cdot t^2 + n^2 \cdot (1 + 6 \cdot t^2)\}$$

$$\lambda_2 = -\frac{n^2 \cdot \sin^2 B}{12 \cdot \rho^2}$$

$$\lambda_3 = -\frac{n^2}{1440 \cdot \rho^4} \cdot (1 + 15 \cdot t^2)$$

$$\lambda_4 = \frac{n^2 \cdot \cos^2 B}{720 \cdot \rho^4} \cdot (-1 - 10 \cdot t^2 + 15 \cdot t^4)$$

$$\lambda_5 = \frac{n^2 \cdot \cos^4 B}{240 \cdot \rho^4} \cdot (-3 \cdot t^2 + t^4)$$

$$v = \sqrt{1 + n^2} \text{ und } n^2 = e'^2 \cdot \cos^2 B$$

$$t = \tan B$$

c)

$$z_1 = \cos \frac{\Delta \bar{L}}{2} \cdot \cos \frac{\Delta \bar{B}}{2}$$

$$z_2 = -\cos \frac{\Delta \bar{L}}{2} \cdot \sin \frac{\Delta \bar{B}}{2}$$

$$n_1 = -\sin \frac{\Delta \bar{L}}{2} \cdot \sin \bar{B}$$

$$n_2 = \sin \frac{\Delta \bar{L}}{2} \cdot \cos \bar{B}$$

$$\bar{s} = 2 \cdot \arctan \sqrt{\frac{z_2^2 + n_2^2}{z_1^2 + n_1^2}}$$

d)

$$S = \frac{a}{V \cdot \rho} \cdot \bar{s} \cdot (1 + \sigma_1 \cdot \Delta B^2 + \sigma_2 \cdot \Delta L^2 + \sigma_3 \cdot \Delta B^4 + \sigma_4 \cdot \Delta B^2 \cdot \Delta L^2 + \sigma_5 \cdot \Delta L^4)$$

$$\sigma_1 = \frac{n^2}{24 \cdot \rho^2 \cdot v^4} \cdot \{1 - t^2 + n^2 \cdot (1 + 6 \cdot t^2)\}$$

$$\sigma_2 = \frac{n^2 \cdot \sin^2 B}{12 \cdot \rho^2} \quad (= -\lambda_2)$$

$$\sigma_3 = \frac{n^2}{480 \cdot \rho^4} \cdot (-1 + t^2)$$

$$\sigma_4 = \frac{n^2 \cdot \cos^2 B}{720 \cdot \rho^4} \cdot (1 - 2 \cdot t^2 - 15 \cdot t^4)$$

$$\sigma_5 = \frac{n^2 \cdot \cos^4 B}{720 \cdot \rho^4} \cdot (9 \cdot t^2 - 5 \cdot t^4) \quad .$$

We compare this model with the spherical model, see the following table:

1.place-2.place	distance with spherical model[km]	distance with Jordan[km]
Berlin-Bonn	454.059	455.227
Göttingen-Bonn	217.832	218.385
Stuttgart-Bonn	264.119	264.190
Frankfort-Bonn	129.452	129.711
Paris-Bonn	402.073	402.859
Hamburg-Bonn	369.206	369.394

At last we treat the Moritz's method for distances larger than 1000km:

$$a) \Delta L = L_2 - L_1 .$$

$$b) C_0 = \arctan\left\{\frac{1}{\sin \Delta L} \cdot \sqrt{\tan^2 B_1 + \tan^2 B_2 - 2 \cdot \tan B_1 \cdot \tan B_2 \cdot \cos \Delta L}\right\} .$$

$$c) u_1 = \arcsin\left\{\frac{\sin B_1}{\sin C_0}\right\} \quad u_2 = \arcsin\left\{\frac{\sin B_2}{\sin C_0}\right\} .$$

$$\Delta u = u_2 - u_1$$

$$\Delta \tan u = \tan u_2 - \tan u_1$$

$$\Delta \tan^3 u = \tan^3 u_2 - \tan^3 u_1$$

$$\Delta \tan^5 u = \tan^5 u_2 - \tan^5 u_1$$

$$\Delta \tan^7 u = \tan^7 u_2 - \tan^7 u_1$$

$$\Delta \sin(2 \cdot u) = \sin(2 \cdot u_2) - \sin(2 \cdot u_1)$$

$$\Delta \sin(4 \cdot u) = \sin(4 \cdot u_2) - \sin(4 \cdot u_1)$$

$$\Delta \sin(6 \cdot u) = \sin(6 \cdot u_2) - \sin(6 \cdot u_1) .$$

$$\begin{aligned}
d) \quad (0,1) &= -\frac{1}{\sin C_0} \cdot \Delta \tan u \\
(0,2) &= \frac{1}{2} \cdot \frac{\cot C_0}{\sin C_0} \cdot (2 \cdot \Delta \tan u + \Delta \tan^3 u) \\
(0,3) &= -\frac{1}{6} \cdot \frac{\cot^2 C_0}{\sin C_0} \cdot \{(6 + 2 \cdot \tan^2 C_0) \cdot \Delta \tan u + (7 + \tan^2 C_0) \cdot \Delta \tan^3 u + 3 \cdot \Delta \tan^5 u\} \\
(0,4) &= \frac{1}{24} \cdot \frac{\cot^3 C_0}{\sin C_0} \cdot \{(24 + 16 \cdot \tan^2 C_0) \cdot \Delta \tan u + (48 + 20 \cdot \tan^2 C_0) \cdot \Delta \tan^3 u \\
&\quad + (45 + 9 \cdot \tan^2 C_0) \cdot \Delta \tan^5 u + 15 \cdot \Delta \tan^7 u\} \\
(1,1) &= \frac{1}{2} \cdot \cos C_0 \cdot \cot C_0 \cdot (\tan^2 C_0 \cdot \Delta u + \Delta \tan u) \\
(1,2) &= \frac{1}{4} \cdot \cos C_0 \cdot \cot^2 C_0 \cdot \{\tan^2 C_0 \cdot \Delta u - (2 + 3 \cdot \tan^2 C_0) \cdot \Delta \tan u - \Delta \tan^3 u\} \\
(1,3) &= \frac{1}{12} \cdot \cos C_0 \cdot \cot^3 C_0 \cdot \{-\tan^4 C_0 \cdot \Delta u + (6 + 8 \cdot \tan^2 C_0 + 3 \cdot \tan^4 C_0) \cdot \Delta \tan u \\
&\quad + (7 + 6 \cdot \tan^2 C_0) \cdot \Delta \tan^3 u + 3 \cdot \Delta \tan^5 u\} \\
(2,1) &= -\frac{3}{8} \cdot \cos C_0 \cdot \cot C_0 \cdot \left\{ \frac{1}{2} \cdot (\tan^2 C_0 + 3 \cdot \sin^2 C_0) \cdot \Delta u + \cos^2 C_0 \cdot \Delta \tan u \right. \\
&\quad \left. + \frac{1}{4} \cdot \tan^2 C_0 \cdot \sin^2 C_0 \cdot \Delta \sin(2 \cdot u) \right\} \\
(2,2) &= \frac{3}{16} \cdot \cos C_0 \cdot \cot^2 C_0 \cdot \left\{ \frac{1}{2} \cdot (5 \cdot \tan^2 C_0 - 9 \cdot \sin^2 C_0) \cdot \Delta u + (6 - 4 \cdot \cos^2 C_0) \cdot \Delta \tan u \right. \\
&\quad \left. + \cos^2 C_0 \cdot \Delta \tan^3 u - \frac{1}{4} \cdot \tan^2 C_0 \cdot \sin^2 C_0 \cdot \Delta \sin(2 \cdot u) \right\} \\
(3,1) &= \frac{5}{16} \cdot \cos C_0 \cdot \cot C_0 \cdot \left\{ \frac{1}{8} \cdot \tan^2 C_0 \cdot (24 - 36 \cdot \sin^2 C_0 + 15 \cdot \sin^4 C_0) \cdot \Delta u + \cos^4 C_0 \cdot \Delta \tan u \right. \\
&\quad \left. + \frac{1}{4} \cdot \tan^2 C_0 \cdot (3 \cdot \sin^2 C_0 - 2 \cdot \sin^4 C_0) \cdot \Delta \sin(2 \cdot u) + \frac{1}{32} \cdot \tan^2 C_0 \cdot \sin^4 C_0 \cdot \Delta \sin(4 \cdot u) \right\} \\
e) \quad \Delta L_1 &= -\frac{1}{2} \cdot \cos C_0 \cdot \Delta u \\
\Delta L_2 &= \frac{3}{16} \cdot \cos C_0 \cdot \{(2 - \sin^2 C_0) \cdot \Delta u + \frac{1}{2} \cdot \sin^2 C_0 \cdot \Delta \sin(2 \cdot u)\} \\
\Delta L_3 &= \frac{5}{64} \cdot \cos C_0 \cdot \left\{ \frac{1}{2} \cdot (-8 + 8 \cdot \sin^2 C_0 - 3 \cdot \sin^4 C_0) \cdot \Delta u + (-2 \cdot \sin^2 C_0 + \sin^4 C_0) \cdot \Delta \sin(2 \cdot u) \right. \\
&\quad \left. - \frac{1}{8} \cdot \sin^4 C_0 \cdot \Delta \sin(4 \cdot u) \right\}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta L_4 = & \frac{35}{2048} \cdot \cos C_0 \cdot (16 - 24 \cdot \sin^2 C_0 + 18 \cdot \sin^4 C_0 - 5 \cdot \sin^6 C_0) \cdot \Delta u \\ & + \frac{1}{4} \cdot (48 \cdot \sin^2 C_0 - 48 \cdot \sin^4 C_0 + 15 \cdot \sin^6 C_0) \cdot \Delta \sin(2 \cdot u) \\ & + \frac{1}{4} \cdot (6 \cdot \sin^4 C_0 - 3 \cdot \sin^6 C_0) \cdot \Delta \sin(4 \cdot u) + \frac{1}{12} \cdot \sin^6 C_0 \cdot \Delta \sin(6 \cdot u) \}. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{f) } C_1 &= -\frac{1}{(0,1)} \cdot \Delta L_1 \\ C_2 &= -\frac{1}{(0,1)} \cdot \{(0,2) \cdot C_1^2 + (1,1) \cdot C_1 + \Delta L_2\} \\ C_3 &= -\frac{1}{(0,1)} \cdot \{(0,2) \cdot 2 \cdot C_1 \cdot C_2 + (0,3) \cdot C_1^3 + (1,1) \cdot C_2 + (1,2) \cdot C_1^2 + (2,1) \cdot C_1 + \Delta L_3\} \\ C_4 &= -\frac{1}{(0,1)} \cdot \{(0,2) \cdot (2 \cdot C_1 \cdot C_3 + C_2^2) + (0,3) \cdot 3 \cdot C_1^2 \cdot C_2 + (0,4) \cdot C_1^4 + (1,1) \cdot C_3 \\ & \quad + (1,2) \cdot 2 \cdot C_1 \cdot C_2 + (1,3) \cdot C_1^3 + (2,1) \cdot C_2 + (2,2) \cdot C_1^2 + (3,1) \cdot C_1 + \Delta L_4\}. \end{aligned}$$

$$\text{g) } C = C_0 + e^{i^2} \cdot C_1 + e^{i^4} \cdot C_2 + e^{i^6} \cdot C_3 + e^{i^8} \cdot C_4$$

$$\text{h) } U_1 = \arcsin\left(\frac{\sin B_1}{\sin C}\right) \quad U_2 = \arcsin\left(\frac{\sin B_2}{\sin C}\right)$$

$$\Delta U = U_2 - U_1$$

$$\Delta \sin(2 \cdot U) = \sin(2 \cdot U_2) - \sin(2 \cdot U_1)$$

$$\Delta \sin(4 \cdot U) = \sin(4 \cdot U_2) - \sin(4 \cdot U_1)$$

$$\Delta \sin(6 \cdot U) = \sin(6 \cdot U_2) - \sin(6 \cdot U_1)$$

$$\Delta \sin(8 \cdot U) = \sin(8 \cdot U_2) - \sin(8 \cdot U_1)$$

$$\text{i) } S_0 = c \cdot \Delta U$$

$$S_1 = c \cdot \left\{ \frac{1}{4} \cdot (-4 + \sin^2 C) \cdot \Delta U - \frac{3}{8} \cdot \sin^2 C \cdot \Delta \sin(2 \cdot U) \right\}$$

$$\begin{aligned} S_2 = c \cdot \left\{ \frac{1}{64} \cdot (64 - 32 \cdot \sin^2 C + 13 \cdot \sin^4 C) \cdot \Delta U + \frac{1}{32} \cdot (24 \cdot \sin^2 C - 9 \cdot \sin^4 C) \cdot \Delta \sin(2 \cdot U) \right. \\ \left. + \frac{15}{256} \cdot \sin^4 C \cdot \Delta \sin(4 \cdot U) \right\} \end{aligned}$$

$$S_3 = c \cdot \left\{ \frac{1}{256} \cdot (-256 + 192 \cdot \sin^2 C - 156 \cdot \sin^4 C + 45 \cdot \sin^6 C) \cdot \Delta U \right. \\ \left. + \frac{1}{1024} \cdot (-1152 \cdot \sin^2 C + 864 \cdot \sin^4 C - 237 \cdot \sin^6 C) \cdot \Delta \sin(2 \cdot U) \right. \\ \left. + \frac{1}{1024} \cdot (-180 \cdot \sin^4 C + 75 \cdot \sin^6 C) \cdot \Delta \sin(4 \cdot U) - \frac{35}{3072} \cdot \sin^6 C \cdot \Delta \sin(6 \cdot U) \right\}$$

$$S_4 = c \cdot \left\{ \frac{1}{16384} \cdot (16384 - 16384 \cdot \sin^2 C + 19968 \cdot \sin^4 C - 11520 \cdot \sin^6 C + 2577 \cdot \sin^8 C) \cdot \Delta U \right. \\ \left. + \frac{1}{4096} \cdot (6144 \cdot \sin^2 C - 6912 \cdot \sin^4 C + 3792 \cdot \sin^6 C - 819 \cdot \sin^8 C) \cdot \Delta \sin(2 \cdot U) \right. \\ \left. + \frac{1}{16384} \cdot (5760 \cdot \sin^4 C - 4800 \cdot \sin^6 C + 1245 \cdot \sin^8 C) \cdot \Delta \sin(4 \cdot U) \right. \\ \left. + \frac{1}{12288} \cdot (560 \cdot \sin^6 C - 245 \cdot \sin^8 C) \cdot \Delta \sin(6 \cdot U) + \frac{315}{131072} \cdot \sin^8 C \cdot \Delta \sin(8 \cdot U) \right\}.$$

$$j) S = S_0 + e'^2 \cdot S_1 + e'^4 \cdot S_2 + e'^6 \cdot S_3 + e'^8 \cdot S_4.$$

The comparison with the spherical model yields the following table:

1.place-2.place	distance with spherical model[km]	distance with Moritz[km]
Athens-Bonn	1930.536	1932.330
Washington-Bonn	6400.527	6417.549
New York-Bonn	6062.236	6078.943
Ottawa-Bonn	5853.271	5870.686
Algiers-Bonn	1582.732	1581.769
Johannesburg-Bonn	8797.729	8766.390
Rio de Janeiro-Bonn	9554.626	9531.677
Wellington-Bonn	18601.017	18595.607
Madras(India)-Bonn	7703.957	7709.179
Sydney-Bonn	16567.917	16563.979
Buenos Aires-Bonn	11445.966	11422.267
Tokyo-Bonn	9340.826	9364.234
Madrid-Bonn	1418.277	1419.277
Taschkent-Bonn	4766.288	4779.316
Boston-Bonn	5768.577	5784.908

At large distances (more than 1000km) the differences are smaller than 40 km. The largest differences are in north-south direction. This can be explained with the flattening of the earth.

References

- [1] Helmut Sieber "Mathematische Tafeln" 3.edition Ernst Klett Verlag Stuttgart 1970

- [2] Albert Schödlbauer "Rechenformeln und Rechenbeispiele zur Landesvermessung" Wichmann-Skripten Heft 2 Teil 1 Herbert Wichmann Verlag Karlsruhe 1981
- [3] Harald Schröder "Trigonometric problem cases well solved" Wissenschaft und Technik Verlag Berlin 2001